

**PEDAGOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF EDUCATION OF STUDENTS IN A
MILITARY-PATRIOTIC SPIRIT**

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Annotation: This article gives information about the fact that the feeling of the Motherland is a sacred feeling, about the formation and education of young people's love for the Motherland, that patriotism is a universal feeling, about the use of such methods as persuasion, example, exercises, encouragement and competition in the military-patriotic education of students.

Key words: student, military patriotism, pedagogical management, method, activity, persuasion, example, exercise, motivation, competition.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Vatan tuyg'usi muqaddas tuyg'u ekanligi, yoshlarda Vatanga muhabbat tuyg'usini shakllantirish va tarbiyalash, vatanparvarlik umuminsoniy tuyg'u ekanligi, ishontirish, ibrat olish kabi usullardan foydalanish haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan, o'quvchilarni harbiy-vatanparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalashda mashqlar, rag'batlantirish va musobaqalar.

Kalit so'zlar: talaba, harbiy vatanparvarlik, pedagogik boshqaruv, usul, faoliyat, ishontirish, namuna, mashq, motivatsiya, musobaqa.

Аннотация: В данной статье дана информация о том, что чувство Родины является священным чувством, о формировании и воспитании у молодежи любви к Родине, о том, что патриотизм является общечеловеческим чувством, об использовании таких методов, как убеждение, пример, учения, поощрения и соревнования в военно-патриотическом воспитании курсантов.

Ключевые слова: студент, воинской патриотизм, педагогическое руководство, метод, деятельность, убеждение, пример, упражнение, мотивация, соревнование.

Like any complex system, military-patriotic education requires management. Management tasks are multifaceted, but the most important of them is to study the state of the managed system. Here we are talking about the organization of military-patriotic education and its results and other students' attitude to military service, readiness for the defense of the Motherland, and the improvement of these things about making military decisions.

In addition to these main tasks, the report of military-patriotic education and its analysis, the selection and placement of pedagogic personnel, it includes defining and organizing their tasks, as well as supervising and motivating them in this important work.

The important principles of pedagogic management of military-patriotic education are as follows:

- scientific, that is, it is based on taking into account the laws of the development of military-patriotic feelings in students of different ages;
- unity of collective and individual management;
- openness, diligence, participation of the entire pedagogical team in the management of the educational institution;
- each person's personal responsibility for the assigned task;
- organization of military-patriotic education is based on a plan;
- having the ability to select the most important directions in educational work and develop them;
- involving the general public in the process of military-patriotic education and others.

Management activity is, first of all, the task of the administration of the educational institution, which should widely use methodological methods as well as methods of administrative assignment. It is necessary to help teachers and class leaders to develop their pedagogical skills in military-patriotic work, to form positive attitudes such as activity in the educational institution and striving for the final result of these works.

The success of management activities is related to the clear division of tasks among the pedagogical team.

Below we will consider the duties of the administration and teachers of the educational institution in terms of military-patriotic education.

General methods of education are widely used in military-patriotic education. Methods such as persuasion, example, exercise, encouragement, and competition are used in the military-patriotic education of students.

Educational methods perform the tasks of teaching, development, and education according to their characteristics. Prior to the convocation, the head of primary training selects the methods necessary for training according to the program, these methods should ensure the achievement of the intended educational and educational goals.

Below, we consider the main methods of military-patriotic education:
The method of persuasion is the main method that forms and develops students' broad worldview, patriotic feelings, and their main qualities. The leader of the initial training before the military draft directly affects the minds, feelings and will of the students with the help of this method and directs them towards specific goals.

Pattern style - at the basis of this method lies, first of all, the conscious desire of people to imitate positive images and follow them. Readers will be deeply moved by stories about the heroic past of our ancestors, their bravery, and the

bravery of today's selfless officers and soldiers in our Armed Forces. They are proud of the lives of these heroes, seek to follow their example, study their ways of life and try to be like them.

A wide range of forms and methods of education and public propaganda are used in the military-patriotic education of students. It should be remembered that forms of educational work mean ways of organizing collective and individual activities of students aimed at achieving one or another educational goal.

Such forms include:

- lectures;
- documents;
- conversations;
- stories;
- themed nights;
- meetings;
- meetings;
- organizing trips and excursions;
- courage lessons;
- military- sports holidays;

Exercise is a method of repeated repetitions in a complicated state in order to develop and develop skills in an action or technique. During the exercises, students acquire practical skills in the use of weapons and equipment, the rules of their adjustment, tactics, firing, methods of solving technical tasks, line exercises. It is very important for students to understand the purpose and order of the exercises. During learning, complex actions can be divided into parts. In the course of the exercises, one tries to perform the movements correctly first, and then to speed them up. Stimulation techniques are used to activate students' movements and postures.

The motivational method is used to develop positive interests and aspirations in students, to develop self-confidence in them, and to form such qualities as a sense of responsibility for the achieved results, striving for new successes. There are forms of encouragement, which can include praise, thanks, awards, placement of the student's photo on the honor board and others.

A competitive style is a style focused on who can perform an action or a method faster and better. It helps students to develop the spirit of competition, to follow the leaders, and to help those who are lagging behind. The competition method is used in the implementation of actions and methods from the basics of military work, opening fire, line preparation and other subjects, as well as in the submission of regulations.

In-depth knowledge of the forms and methods of military-patriotic education, the rules of their use, allows the head of initial training before military service to carefully plan and organize military-patriotic education and public defense work.

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